

Comparative study of blood glucose control between male and female Type 2 Diabetic Patients in Karbala'a Province

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Introduction

Diabetes is a chronic condition caused by either an absolute lack of insulin or a relative lack of insulin due to impaired insulin secretion and action. Insulin resistance and glucose intolerance results in hyperglycemia and alterations in lipid and protein metabolism. In the long term, these metabolic abnormalities contribute to complications such as cardiovascular disease, retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is very common in all age groups, worldwide (1).

There are several risk factors for the progression of Type 2 DM (T2DM) including family history, obesity, chronic physical inactivity, race or ethnicity, history of impaired fasting glucose, impaired glucose tolerance, HbA1c 5.7% to 6.4%, hypertension, abnormal high-density lipoprotein cholesterol and/or elevated triglyceride levels. The duration of diabetes, lifestyle, level of education, age, number of medications, morbidity, socioeconomic factors and type of insurance coverage, are risk factors for sustained poor glycemic control. Individuals at risk of poor glycemic control may need specific interventions to achieve optimal glycemic control (2).

Inadequate glycemic control among patients with T2DM indicates a major public health issue and a significant risk factor for the progression of diabetic complications. Glycemic control remains the main therapeutic target for prevention of organ damage and other complications arising from diabetes. In clinical practice, achieving optimal glycemic control on a long-term basis is challenging, since the reasons for poor glycemic control in T2DM are complex. Both patient and health care provider-related factors may play a significant role in poor glycemic control (3).

The glycosylated hemoglobin, or A1c has become the gold standard for measuring chronic glycaemia and is the clinical marker for predicting long-term complications, particularly microvascular complications. HbA1c is most commonly measured because it comprises of the majority of glycosylated hemoglobin and is the least affected by recent fluctuations in blood glucose. In epidemiological analyses, glycated hemoglobin (A1c) levels $>7\%$ are associated with a significantly enhanced risk of both Macrovascular and microvascular complications, irrespective of the main treatment. People with diabetes have a greater risk of developing a number of major health problems (4).

There is almost a sex bias with the potential underestimation for the prevalence of diabetes and prediabetes in women due to physiological differences between men and women (5). Nevertheless, increasing evidence has shown that diabetes adversely affects women more than men despite higher prevalence in men. Compared to men with the disease, women with T2DM, regardless of menopausal status, had up to 27% higher excess risk of stroke and 44% higher excess risk of coronary heart disease. They also experience depression and anxiety and thus lowered quality of life, which in turn may negatively affect attitudes towards diabetes self-management and associated behaviors.

In addition to physiological and biological differences, behavioral differences in health-seeking, adherence to treatment and medication regimes, and access to healthcare may also contribute to gender disparities in diabetes care and/or outcomes (6). The presence of gender-specific differences in predisposition, development, and clinical presentation of T2D are related to diversities in biology, culture, lifestyle, environment, and socioeconomic status (7).

Aim of study

To examine gender differences in glycemic control in diabetic patients type 2 in Karbala'a Province

Materials and methods

A cross sectional study was conducted between December 2020 and February 2021 by recruiting 100 T2DM patients attended by a physician or endocrinologist to private labs to do HbA1c test. Gender and age were recorded in addition to the HbA1c% value.

Means and standard deviations (SD) were calculated for continuous variables, whereas frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables. Significant gender differences in demographics and clinical characteristics were determined using the t tests for continuous data and chi-squared tests for categorical data. Two-tailed p values of less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant for this study.

Results and Discussion

Of the 100 patients with T2DM enrolled in this study approximately 60% were women as there is prevalence of diabetes and prediabetes in women due to physiological differences between men and women (5). Compared to men, women in this study tended to be older (55 ± 1.4 vs. 51 ± 1.3 years). The older age of diabetic women revealed the protective role of estrogen in younger ages; while men presented in younger age with DM or other chronic disease because they do not have the coverage protection provided by estrogen (8).

Men had a higher but non-significant (p-value 0.4) mean HbA1c ($10.03\% \pm 0.02$ vs. $9.87\% \pm 0.02$) as in figure (1). This nonsignificant difference may be due to the fact that the Iraqi families has been used to eat together, regardless of being diabetic or not, resulted in uncontrolled hyperglycemia because of the absence of healthy family behaviors. This finding was inconsistent with Tzeyu L.Michaud who reported that women have poor glycemic control more than men (9). Also it was not agreed with Maria Ida Maiorino who stated significant difference in blood glucose control between men and women the detriment of women (10). This disagreement with studies that assisted gender difference in glycemic control may be due to the impact of the poor health care services and the absence of psychosocial interventions.

Figure (1): Difference between male and female in HbA1c%

Forty seven (47) DM patients in the recruited sample had HTN; greater prevalence of hypertension in women (53.1% versus 46.8%) than men; this may be due largely to the fact that mean age of hypertensive women is higher than men (57 ± 12.3 vs. 52 ± 8.9 years). This age group in women represent mostly the period of menopause metabolic complication which is represented mainly as HTN and hyperlipidemia caused by low estrogen hormone concentration. Type 2 diabetes, like other disorders of metabolism, commonly manifests during the mid-life and thus coincides with the timing of the menopausal transition in women also the mid-life is a vulnerable period for the development of obesity which represent a risk factor for developing DM (11). This result were consistent with the facts reviewed by Narayan KM et al (12). However, this difference in age did not reflect significant difference in glycemic control (p-value is 0.1) as represented in figure (2).

Figure (2): Difference in HbA1c between male & female having HTN with DM

The poor glycemic control in both genders having chronic disease may be resulted from the costly and limited health services in Iraq. This problem came in accordance with N Whichit *et al* who stated that medical, nursing, and social services provide essential support for individuals living with a chronic condition, these services are often costly and limited in community settings in both developed and developing countries (13). However those community health practices, if in place, provide invaluable support to patients with a chronic illness, they cannot provide the continuous follow-up required to fully meet patients' needs as reported by T Bodenheimer *et al* (14).

Patients without concomitant HTN also had nonsignificant difference in high HbA1c% level (p-value is 0.3) as presented in figure (3). The females in this group had non-significant higher mean age than males (54 ± 9.3 vs. 49 ± 7.8 years). This poor glycemic control represented by high HbA1c% in both genders reflect poor health services accompanied by the absence of health care strategies involving family members which can improve self-efficacy, knowledge about the condition, and self-care skills in individuals with a chronic condition such as T2DM. This explanation came in agree with AA Baig *et al* in their conclusion that they found evidence for improvement in patients' self-efficacy, perceived social support, diabetes knowledge, and diabetes self-care across the studies (15). The same result of the family role were achieved by JM Dalton *et al* in his pilot study (16).

Figure (3): Difference between male and female with DM only in HbA1c% level

As both genders exposed to the same low quality health services and poor family-oriented interventions, so the factors separate the glycemc control of both genders subsided behind the main impact of the poor Psychosocial interventions which could provide emotional and psychological support to patients with diabetes, help to develop healthy family behaviors, and promote diabetes self-management. In addition to that age groups exposed to diabetes in the range of 50 years old and more are mostly low educated level, so the presence of health oriented family members could improve patients' self-efficacy and overall management of their diabetes.

Conclusion

There was similar poor glycemc control in both genders in Karbala'a Province.

Recommendations

- Provide low cost health measures to follow up diabetic patients regarding glycemic control.
- Establishing of family-oriented health care programs to assist in providing sufficient glycemic control on diabetic patients.

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